

THE NATURE OF TRAUMATIC INJURIES OF THE ORAL MUCOSA IN CHILDREN**Aliyev M.,***Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine
Department of Terapeutik Dentistry Assistant
Azerbaijan Medical University
Baku, Azerbaijan***Jalilova G.,***Department of Pediatrik Dentistry Assistant
Azerbaijan Medical University
Baku, Azerbaijan***Kalbiyeva N.***Department of Pediatrik Dentistry Assistant
Azerbaijan Medical University
Baku, Azerbaijan*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7688765>**Abstract**

The clinical course of traumatic injuries of the oral mucosa in children depends on the anatomical and physiological age-related features. The aim of the study was to evaluate the features of trauma to the oral mucosa in children. A retrospective study of 70 patient histories was conducted. The average age was 12 years. The main cause of injury in children was mechanical damage - 76%. Thermal 10 (14.28%) and chemical injuries - 7 (10%) of the oral mucosa were recorded much less frequently. By the nature of the damage, single erosions (26.86%) of ulcers were most often detected - 20% and multiple erosions - 16%. In 33% of cases, traumatic lesion of the COR in children was associated with dental treatment.

Keywords: oral mucosa, trauma, ulcer, erosion, iatrogenic lesions.

The mucous membrane of the oral cavity (OM) as the initial part of the digestive tract from the first hours after the birth of a child and throughout his life is subjected to a variety of local influences associated with the function of the organs of the oral cavity, and also, to a greater or lesser extent, reflects all physiological and pathological processes that take place in the human body. The degree of damage and clinical manifestations depend on the nature of the stimulus, the time and strength of exposure, and the individual characteristics of the child's body [1]. Age-related features play a major role in the occurrence and course of traumatic injuries of the COR in children. So, in newborns, there is a low differentiation of the epithelium and connective tissue, the epithelial cover is thin and consists of only two layers of cells, the basement membrane in all parts of the oral cavity is thin and tender. In the early childhood period, regional differences are formed, however, the fibers of the own layer of the mucous membrane are loose and have a thin and delicate structure. These structural features undoubtedly determine the increased vulnerability of the oral mucosa in children. In school-children, the maturity of collagen fibers increases, the number of protein structures in the epithelial layer increases, the mucous membrane becomes more dense and resistant to traumatic effects. However, during puberty, the changes that occur under the influence of hormonal regulation factors increase, which entails an increased response to chronic injury with a pronounced vascular component [1]. Traumatic injuries of the oral mucosa in children are caused by physical influences, which include mechanical, thermal, chemical, electrical and radiation. Mechanical traumatic injuries are also di-

vided into acute and chronic [2]. When studying the literature data, we found that information on the prevalence of such injuries is scarce, however, the degree of injury in children is nevertheless high. This is the reason for the relevance of this topic [4]. Purpose of the study

Evaluation of the features of the occurrence of trauma to the oral mucosa in children.

Materials and methods

A retrospective study was carried out according to the case histories of pediatric patients who applied to the multidisciplinary dental clinic of the Ural State Medical University for trauma to the oral mucosa. We analyzed 70 case histories of patients aged 2 to 17 years. The average age was 12 years. Of the patients, there were 47 girls (67.14), which is 2 times higher than the number of boys, which was 23 (32.86). Among the victims, children aged 14 years prevail, the total number of which is 11 people (15.71%). The nature of the elements of the COR lesion, the role of individual factors in the occurrence of mucosal injury, and the localization of lesions were studied. In the analysis of age, the arithmetic mean values and the sample standard deviation were determined. We also calculated the percentage characterizing the proportion of children with a certain trait in the sample.

Results and its discussion

In the patients examined by us, mechanical traumatic injuries were most often detected 53 (75.71%). This is consistent with literature data. At the same time, 25 (47.17%) children applied to the dental clinic with acute injuries. The remaining 28 (52.83) applied for chronic mechanical injury. Much less common were thermal injuries - 10 (14.28%) and chemical injuries -

7 (10%) of the oral mucosa. In one case, we observed the development of traumatic damage to the COR against the background of chemotherapy treatment of a child for cancer, so it was assigned to a separate group. The main element of the lesion in the examination of children with ORS injury were multiple (16%) and single (26.86%) erosions, the total number of people with erosions was 30. Thus, damage to the oral mucosa in children is more often superficial and localized in within the epithelial layer. In second place in terms of frequency of occurrence were ulcers detected in 14 (20%) children. Less common were such elements of damage as wounds - in 9 (12.86%) and foci of hyperkeratosis - in 6 (8.58%) children. Foci of epithelial desquamation were found in 4 cases (5.72%), necrosis - in 4 (5.72%) cases, aphthae, hematomas and hyperemia spots - in 2 (2.85%) cases. The bubble was found in 1 (1.42%) child. The lower occurrence of these elements is due to their more specific etiology. Most often, injuries were localized in the area of the mucous membrane of the upper and lower lips - 17 (25%). This is due to the fact that the lips limit the vestibule of the oral cavity and are often the first to encounter aggressive environmental factors. Quite often, the lesions were localized on the mucous membrane of the cheeks - 12 (18%). Less commonly, traumatic injuries were detected in the hard palate (13.5%), tongue (12%), alveolar processes (12%), transitional fold (7.5%), gums (6%), frenulum of the upper lip (3%) and at the bottom of the mouth (3%). When studying the etiology of traumatic lesions of the COR in children, chronic biting often acted as a damaging factor. It was detected in 11 children (16.5%). This phenomenon in childhood may be associated with an anomaly in the location of the teeth and pathology of the bite, destruction of the crowns of the lateral teeth or filling defects (sharp edges), and also be in the nature of a bad habit caused by psychogenic factors. It should be noted that prolonged exposure to this factor leads to significant changes in the mucous membrane and underlying tissues, accompanied by pronounced hyperplastic processes. Being an optional precancer, such lesions require immediate medical action to eliminate the etiological factor. In the vast majority of cases, the elimination of the cause leads to a quick recovery, despite the severity of morphological changes in the tissues. Often, the injury was associated with damage to the COR with solid food - 15%. This may be due to the fact that the epithelial layer of the palate in childhood has a smaller layer of keratinized cells and inaccurate and hasty chewing of solid food leads to injury to the mucous membrane. Less often, thermal injuries - burns and frostbite - acted as an etiological factor. Thermal injuries often occur as a result of haste when eating, and in the case of young children, due to parental oversight. We identified thermal lesions in 7 (10.5%) cases, external injuries - in 6 (9%), trauma with a sharp edge of the tooth - in 5 (7.5%), after using personal oral hygiene products - in 5 (7.5%). One of the reasons for the appearance of defects in the oral mucosa

was the state of the body after chemotherapy - 1 (1.5%), which is due to the fact that many chemotherapeutic substances reduce the degree of growth of cancer cells and at the same time affect normal, rapidly dividing cells of the gastrointestinal tract. Separately, it is necessary to single out such an etiological factor as iatrogenesis, which was detected in 22 patients (33%). Iatrogenic injuries were the adverse effects of preventive, diagnostic and therapeutic interventions during or after dental appointments. Of all the iatrogenies, injuries caused by orthodontic structures quite often acted as a traumatic factor - 6 (27%), the consequences of injection anesthesia - 5 (23%). Less often, traumatic damage to the mucous membrane occurred after professional oral hygiene - 14%, the use of a laser and the use of a devitalizing paste (9% each). A very specific complication of dental treatment for children is anesthesiophagia - significant damage to soft tissues as a result of biting and chewing by a child of a numb mucous membrane after local anesthesia. Basically, this lesion occurs in the region of the lower lip, but it can also be localized on the upper lip and cheek. Deep ulcers, of course, cause concern for parents and cause, albeit temporary, but significant damage to the health of the child. Prevention of this complication is a reasonable choice of the type and dose of local anesthetic, warning parents about the need to monitor the child immediately after the treatment. It is important to note that direct trauma during dental treatment can indirectly affect the occurrence of damage to the mucous membrane - for example, lead to the activation of a viral infection dormant in the body. Also, a frequent case of iatrogenesis is damage to the oral mucosa in children with equipment elements during orthodontic treatment.

References:

1. Kodirova M.T. Sovremennyj podhod lechenija hronicheskogo recidivirujushhego aftoznogo stomatita u detej v podrozkovom vozraste. / Abbasova DB // Molodoj uchenyj». Mezhdunarodnyj nauchnyj zhurnal, 2020. № 6. S. 296.
2. Vinogradova T.F., Maksimova O.P., Mel'nichenko Je.M. Zabolevanija parodonta i slizistoj obolochki polosti rta u detej. M.: Medicina, 1983, 208 s., il.
3. Burieva N.A., Mahsumova I.Sh. Profilakticheskaja rabota v aspekte stomatologicheskikh zabolevanij //bbk 60 s 56, 2019. S. 185.
4. Elizarova V.M., Strahova S.Ju., Drobot'ko L.N. Osnovnye zabolevanija slizistoj obolochki polosti rta u detej. 2007. – 10 s.
5. Leont'eva V.K., Kisel'nikova L.P. Detskaja terapevticheskaja stomatologija. Nacional'noe rukovodstvo. M.: GJeOTAR-Media, 2010. – 625 s.
6. Chizhevskij I.V. Mehanicheskie travmaticheskie povrezhdenija slizistoj obolochki polosti rta u detej rannego i doshkol'nogo vozrasta / Chizhevskij I.V., Ermakova I.D., Zabyshnyj A.A., Zhurba O.O. // Zbirnik statej. – 2013. – №2 (17). – S. 325-328.